

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Volume 1, No.10. of J.UCS contains two papers on multimedia and hypermedia systems, and one of a more theoretical nature. Hope you will enjoy them!

As some of you know, the refereeing process in J.UCS works as follows: abstracts of submitted papers go to all editors (over 170), and editors interested in refereeing the paper at issue then receive the full paper. This works better than sending papers to referees for review for obvious reasons. It also produces surprises: the paper on "Authoring on the Fly" evidently was very intriguing from both title and abstract so that over 20 editors asked to review it! We thus expect that the paper will also be extremely popular with readers.

Here is another bit of news, and a bit of good news, indeed: the whole volume 1 of J.UCS including all necessary tools to peruse it will be pressed on a CD-ROM by Springer by February 96...together with titles and information on Springer publications: for this reason 30.000 (!!!) CD's will be pressed, giving J.UCS and all the papers in J.UCS much visibility. Thus, if you still want to make sure that one of your papers is widely distributed (more widely than with most other publications) hurry up and submit your manuscript for the December issue.

Cordially

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Dr. H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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